

LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF CHILDBEARING CARE AMONG MOTHERS IN SELECTED REMOTE COMMUNITIES IN GENERAL SANTOS CITY

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive study determined the level of awareness of childbearing care among mothers in six (6) selected remote communities in General Santos City. A validated self-made Childbearing Care Awareness Questionnaire Tool was used to determine the demographic profile and the level of awareness of childbearing care among eighteen (18) pregnant mothers who were selected through quota sampling. The study showed that most of the respondents were aged 18-25 years old, married, had 1-2 children, with monthly income of below 5,000, had reached a high school level of education, and with hypertension in the health history. The findings revealed that most respondents are moderately aware of various aspects of childbearing care. It revealed that the highest awareness of mothers was on nutrition and the lowest was in terms of immunization. Therefore, this study recommends establishing a pregnancy care educational program to increase the awareness of mothers on the essentials of childbearing care. This study also recommends further research to investigate the effects of demographic profiles on the level of awareness of mothers. Further research is also recommended to expand the locale of the study to other remote communities to explore different approaches to investigate the extent of low awareness of mothers on childbearing care practices.

Keywords: *Awareness, Childbearing Care, Nutrition, Immunization, Pregnancy Care Educational Program*

INTRODUCTION

Childbearing care is one of the most important components of health care for every woman of reproductive age (Lu and Halfon, 2013). It is a form of care that provides a series of interventions before conception intending to identify and modify biomedical, behavioral, and psychosocial risks to women's health or pregnancy outcomes through prevention and management (Moos, 2010). Childbearing care includes education, screening, counseling, treatment, monitoring, and promoting the well-being of the mother and fetus (Shafqat, Fayaz, Rahim, & Saima, 2105). It is based on providing women and their families with appropriate advice and information that may help them to be in good health during pregnancy, delivery, and postnatal recovery. Also, providing mothers with appropriate supplements such as folic acid and vitamins that are needed during pregnancy (Rajiv, 2015).

Good caring during pregnancy is so important for the health of the mother and the development of the unborn baby, it links the woman and her family with a formal health system which will increase the chance of using a skilled attendant, particularly at birth, and contributes to good health through the life cycle. At any healthcare delivery system, childbearing care is considered a backbone of obstetrical services, it is substantial for the health of pregnant women and it is how maternal and fetal complications are determined and managed (Rajiv, 2015). Roughly, a thousand mothers all around the world die daily due to pregnancy and delivery-related causes (Anjum, Noor, & Bano, 2015) which resemble 25% of maternal deaths according to the World Health Organization.

Pregnancy-related deaths have been increasing in the United States. Maternal mortality ratios in the United States had increased about 3% from 2000-2015. Moreover, women in rural and underserved communities face additional risks and challenges that could lead to higher rates of maternal mortality and other severe health complications (American Pregnancy Association, 2015). According to Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2015), in most rural counties which includes areas with populations of less than 50,000 residents, the maternal mortality ratio was 23.8 deaths per 100,000 live births compared to 14.6 in large metropolitan counties.

According to the estimate made in 2013 by the National Demographic Health Survey, maternal deaths account for 32% of all deaths among women between the age group of 15–49 years. The lifetime risk indicates that 1 in 30 women will die as a result of pregnancy or childbirth (National Population Commission, 2013). Most of these complications predate pregnancy and get worsened during pregnancy, thereby causing a lot of pregnancy-related morbidities or mortality. No wonder 4 out of every 10 women have been reported to have unplanned pregnancies, therefore making it difficult to address any premorbid condition or lifestyle that can affect the outcome of that pregnancy (Singh, Sedgh, Hussain, 2010)

Research Questions

This study generally aims to determine the level of awareness of mothers in terms of childbearing care. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of mothers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Civil status;
 - 1.3 Number of children;
 - 1.4 Monthly income;
 - 1.5 Educational attainment;
 - 1.6 Health history?

2. What is the level of awareness of mothers on childbearing care in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 Nutrition;
 - 2.2 Prenatal care;
 - 2.3 Lifestyle practices;
 - 2.4 Immunization?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in six remote communities in General Santos City comprising three puroks in Barangay Upper Labay and another three puroks in Barangay Olympog. The respondents were eighteen pregnant mothers who were selected through quota sampling. The demographic profile and mothers' awareness of childbearing care were determined using a self-made Childbearing Care Awareness Questionnaire Tool validated by three academicians. The tool also underwent pilot testing to ensure the instrument was appropriate for the target population. The data-gathering procedures started by obtaining permission from the Barangay Captains of Barangay Upper Labay and Barangay Olympog. After this, the researcher sought assistance from the Barangay Health Workers in determining pregnant mothers then informed consents were provided to ensure that the purpose, risks, and benefits of participating in the study were thoroughly explained. After obtaining the needed information, descriptive data analysis was employed to provide interpretation and meanings to the gathered information about the profile of respondents and their awareness of childbearing care. This study was limited only to determining awareness of various aspects of childbearing care such as nutrition, prenatal care, lifestyle practices, and immunization while other aspects such as family planning and delivery were not included. As recommended by the local government of General Santos City, the study was conducted only in two barangays with three puroks each due to the ease of access to the place and the extent of assistance that could be provided.

RESULTS

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variables	N=18	Percentage
Age		
18-25 years old	13	72.2
26-30 years old	4	22.2
31-35 years old	1	5.6
Civil Status		
Single	3	16.7
Married	11	61.1
Cohabiting	0	0
Widowed	4	22.2
Number of Children		
1-2	9	50.0
3-5	7	38.9
6-8	2	11.1
9 and above	0	0
Monthly Income		
Below 5,000	11	61.1
5,001-10,000	5	27.8
10,001 and above	2	11.1
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Level	4	22.2
Elementary Graduate	3	16.7
High School Level	6	33.2
High School Graduate	1	5.6
College Level	3	16.7
College Graduate	1	5.6
Health History		
Hypertension	8	44.4
Diabetes Mellitus	4	22.2
Tuberculosis	5	27.8
Kidney Disease	1	5.6

Table 2. Level of Awareness of Childbearing Care of Mothers

Variables	Mean	Interpretation
Aspects of Childbearing Care		
Nutrition	3.87	Moderate
Prenatal care	3.10	Moderate
Lifestyle Practices	3.42	Moderate
Immunization	2.95	Moderate
Over-all Mean	3.10	Moderate

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of respondents. It revealed that most of the respondents were aged 18-25 years old, married, had 1-2 children, with monthly income of below 5,000, had reached a high school level of education, and with hypertension in the health history.

Table 2 depicts the level of awareness of childbearing care. It showed that most respondents are moderately aware of various aspects of childbearing care which obtained an overall mean of 3.10. It revealed that nutrition obtained the highest mean of 3.87 which was interpreted as moderately aware while immunization obtained the lowest mean of 2.95 which was interpreted as moderately aware.

Adequate nutrition is crucial for maternal and child health, both before and during pregnancy. Malnutrition in pregnancy is associated with nutrient deficiency-related complications and outcomes for both mother and child (McCarthy, Murray, & Kiely, 2022). There is also growing evidence that various adverse outcomes are more readily prevented by beginning interventions before conception (Mahajan, Singh, & Shah, 2014). However, awareness of the importance of preconception health and nutrition appears low, resulting in missed opportunities to support proper growth and development (Mitchell, Levis, & Prue, 2012).

Immunization of pregnant women allows for delivering protective antibodies to the fetus and protection to have received childhood immunizations at the time of exposure. In the absence of maternally derived pathogen-antigen-specific antibodies, infants remain vulnerable to severe disease until they have established an adequate protective antibody response (Gessner, Katz, Johnson, Skidmore, Knight, & Bhat, 2015). Enhancing confidence in immunization by increasing the evidence-base for safety during pregnancy, and access by incorporating immunization into standard models of antenatal care is likely to improve uptake (Kourtis, Read, & Jamieson, 2014).

Knowledge and healthy childbearing practices during pregnancy are crucial aspects for mothers to possess to have a successful outcome of delivery. Childbearing care is a useful practice for lowering infant and maternal mortality. Therefore, the present study was planned to identify the awareness regarding childbearing care among pregnant women. Pregnancy care is an effective tool to reduce both infant and maternal mortality and morbidity. The principle of childbearing care is to provide advice, education, reassurance, and support to address and treat the problems associated with childbearing and to provide effective screening during pregnancy.

Conclusions

This study indicates that most pregnant mothers in remote communities showed moderate awareness of childbearing care which could affect maternal and child health outcomes as well as the health decisions for a healthy pregnancy. Awareness of these

aspects of childbearing care is necessary for a successful outcome of pregnancy, preventing possible complications during pregnancy and after delivery, and subsequently maternal and child mortality and morbidity.

Recommendations

This study recommends establishing a pregnancy care educational program to increase the awareness of mothers on the necessary childbearing care. This program aims to prepare expectant women and their partners or support persons for essential childbirth, breastfeeding, and infant care. The offering of pregnancy educational programs constitutes a major aspect of health promotion within public health addressing poor awareness of mothers in necessary practices of bearing a child. This study also recommends further research to investigate the effects of demographic profiles on the level of awareness of mothers on childbearing care. Further research is also recommended to expand the locale of study to other remote communities to explore or apply different approaches to investigate the extent of low awareness of mothers on childbearing care practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research study followed a standard ethical guideline. The participation of respondents was voluntary. They were to opt to dismiss themselves from the study at any point whenever they felt uncomfortable. Their participation was protected from harm. The dignity and well-being of respondents were also protected. The research data remained confidential throughout the study, and the rights of respondents were protected while ensuring scientific or academic integrity. There was no bias in the interpretation of the results and were used for research purposes.

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